

CHEMICAL, MORPHOLOGICAL AND MECHANICAL CHARACTERIZATION OF THE INTERPHASE OF POLYMER MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Detailed physical and mechanical characterization of the interphases of polymer matrix composites can lead to a more complete understanding of failure mechanisms in polymer matrix composite (PMC). This work investigates the nanoscopic nature of PMC interphases in terms of topography, chemical mapping/bonding and modulus to find a bridge between nanoscopic, microscopic and macroscopic mechanical properties. It is guided by ongoing simulations aimed at an understanding of bond scission, interphase structure and mechanical properties at the nanoscale level via a multiscale computational approach. DGEBA epoxy resins with known chemical structures are processed in-house with controlled stoichiometric ratios (resin and cross-linker) and degrees of cure, both in the presence and absence of carbon fiber. FTIR (mid-IR and near-IR) is used to investigate the chemical structure of the bulk, and AFM-IR is used to investigate the chemical structure at the nanoscale. The chemical mapping results show that there is a variation in the chemical network structure between the bulk and the interphase as well as within the bulk matrix. Control experiments using spectroscopy and thermal analysis confirm that this variability in the three-dimensional network is due to differences in cross-linker density and degree of cure. These network structure variations result in changes in thermal and mechanical properties in the bulk as well as at the interphase.

1 INTRODUCTION

Understanding the root causes of mechanical damage in structural composites such as polymers and polymer matrix composites (PMCs) is crucial for improving the durability of these materials, and the knowledge gained can be integrated into computational simulation tools, enhancing the accuracy of

simulations for remaining life predictions. One of the key damage mechanisms comes in the form of microcracks, which are usually initiated in the interphase region. The interphase is a three-dimensional reinforcing region between the fiber and the polymer matrix [1] where detection is difficult and repair is almost impossible. The chemical, physical and mechanical properties of the interphase are known to differ distinctly from those of the fiber and the bulk polymer matrix. Variations in properties across the interphase play a major role in optimizing the mechanical performance of the composite.[2] To avoid catastrophic failure, deeper physical and chemical understanding of the interphase at the nanoscale has become a key priority for both experiment and theory. Despite the great interest, [3, 4] characterizing the interphase zone and its properties experimentally remains a significant challenge that has precluded the incorporation of these properties into multiscale materials simulations.

The three-dimensional chemical network structure of the interphase in PMCs is still ambiguous. It is yet a significant challenge to extract fundamental properties such as thermal (glass transition, melting) and mechanical (modulus / strength / toughness) properties and rely heavily on indirect or numerical methods.[5-10] For example, Kim et al. characterized the interphase in glass fiber reinforced vinyl ester composites with nano scratch and found that the effective thickness of the interphase varies from 0.8 nm to 1.5 nm depending on the type and concentration of silane agent.[11] Munz et al. reported a 20-80 nm width of the interphase in carbon fiber epoxy composites by measuring the stiffness using atomic force microscopy (AFM) in force modulation mode.[12] Recent advances in multifaceted characterization techniques including AFM[12-16] and transmission electron microscope (TEM) electron energy loss spectroscopy (EELS)[17] have created new opportunities to evaluate some of these properties, although characterization remains a complex problem as those properties vary depending on the resin chemistry, fiber surface chemistry, and the exact processing conditions (temperature, cure cycle).

This work investigates the nanoscopic nature of interphases of PMCs in terms of topography, chemical mapping/bonding and modulus to find a bridge between the chemistry and the mechanics. It is guided by ongoing simulations aimed at an understanding of bond scission, interphase structure and mechanical properties at the nanoscale level through a multiscale computational approach. [18-20]

2 EXPERIMENTAL

EPON (Momentive) pre-polymers system (828 and 834) with two molecular weights in the range 380 g/mol to 570 g/mol were chosen. 3,3'-diaminodiphenyl sulfone (DDS) (Sigma) was chosen as a cross-linker because of its ability to result in very high cross-linking density (>99%) compared to other linkers.[21] T-300 carbon fiber (Toray) was chosen due to its sizing compatibility with the epoxy system. PMCs were cured under two different conditions to see the influence of degree of cure (Table 1): a) 1st cycle – 125 °C for 5 h and 2nd cycle – 200 °C for 1 h; and b) 1st cycle – 125 °C for 2.5 h and 2nd cycle – 200 °C for 0.5 h, for fully cured and partially cured samples, respectively. Samples were prepared with stoichiometric ratios (epoxy:amine) of 2:1 and 4:1 for each curing condition to investigate the influence of cross-linker density. The morphology and chemical composition of the interphase were investigated by preparing cross-sectioned samples via cutting the specimen and following with slow polishing.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1 shows the schematics of an epoxy (DGEBA), a cross-linker (3,3 DDS) and a cross-linked epoxy chain after the reaction. Depending on the stoichiometric ratio of the reactants and the curing conditions (temperature and time), the reactivity of the components can be altered. Typically, each primary amine can react twice with epoxy molecules, ultimately influencing its three-dimensional network structure. Reactivity will be further affected by the presence of a fiber around the interface/interphase region due to: a) reactions between the sizing molecules and the epoxy/cross-linkers, and b) diffusion of epoxy/cross-linker molecules. To understand the chemical network

structure and properties of the interphase, it is also very important to understand the bulk structure. Hence, specimens were also prepared without any fiber (Table 1), for which a silicon mold with a rectangular geometry (9 cm length, 1.5 cm width, and 0.2 cm thickness) was used. The specimens were polished with a grinder (after curing) to achieve optimized dimensions. Quantitative estimation of the degree of cure was done by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) and Fourier-transform near-infrared spectroscopy (FT-NIR). In parallel, molecular dynamics simulations of identical materials were carried out to guide the experimental effort. Three-dimensional cross-linked systems with ~ 30,000 atoms were built in Materials Studio, with degrees of cure and cross-linker density built to match the experimental values. Simulations were conducted by the CVFF force field using Discover, utilizing our recently developed quantum mechanics-molecular mechanics framework. [18, 19] This has enabled the prediction of bond scission under load, creation of intermittent free radicals, and exploration of the potential energy surface for possible secondary reactions immediately following bond scission (Fig. 1e).

Name	EPON	Stoichiometric Ratio (Epoxy:Amine)	Curing Condition
828-2-1-FC	828	2:1	1 st Cycle = 125°C - 5 h 2 nd Cycle = 200°C - 1 h
828-4-1-FC	828	4:1	1 st Cycle = 125°C - 5 h 2 nd Cycle = 200°C - 1 h
828-2-1-PC	828	2:1	1 st Cycle = 125°C - 2.5 h 2 nd Cycle = 200°C - 0.5 h
828-2-1-PC	828	4:1	1 st Cycle = 125°C - 2.5 h 2 nd Cycle = 200°C - 0.5 h
834-2-1-FC	834	2:1	1 st Cycle = 125°C - 5 h 2 nd Cycle = 200°C - 1 h
834-4-1-FC	834	4:1	1 st Cycle = 125°C - 5 h 2 nd Cycle = 200°C - 1 h
834-2-1-PC	834	2:1	1 st Cycle = 125°C - 2.5 h 2 nd Cycle = 200°C - 0.5 h
834-4-1-PC	834	4:1	1 st Cycle = 125°C - 2.5 h 2 nd Cycle = 200°C - 0.5 h

*FC = Fully cured, PC = Partially cured

Table 1. Description of the samples prepared by varying molecular weight, cross-linker density and degree of cure.

Detailed characterizations were conducted to evaluate experimentally how the chemical network structure affected the mechanical load in epoxy systems. Spectroscopy (X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy, FT-Infrared spectroscopy), microscopy (HRTEM, AFM-IR, SEM), and mechanical testing (3-point bending) were all utilized to understand the chemical network structure and its influence on the mechanics. FTIR analysis in the mid-IR (MIR) region was carried out on DGEBA, 3,3DDS and cured epoxy (Fig. 2a) to understand the influence of curing on the spectra. The aromatic C-H peak of epoxy at 1607 cm⁻¹ shifted to 1597 cm⁻¹ after the reaction. This shift was due to a reaction of the aromatic amine with the epoxy, where 3,3 DDS showed a doublet 1597 cm⁻¹ (major) and 1619 cm⁻¹ (minor) due to C-H bending and N-H bending, respectively. Similarly, an almost symmetric peak at 1507 cm⁻¹ (C-H bending) is seen in DGEBA, whereas in a cured product, a doublet appeared at 1507 cm⁻¹ and 1494 cm⁻¹. This is another key signature of the reaction. On the other hand, 3,3 DDS showed a sharp peak at 1482 cm⁻¹ (aromatic C=C). In spite of this analysis, it is not possible to get well-isolated peaks in the MIR spectra due to the overlap of the bands, which leads to complications in

obtaining quantitative analysis via infrared spectroscopy. Complementary to MIR, near-infrared (NIR) region of the spectrum (10000 to 4000 cm^{-1}) has well-isolated absorption bands of the functional groups of interest in epoxy resin cure reactions. It includes primary amine, secondary amine, and hydroxyl groups resulting from overtone and combination bands. Figure 2b shows the FT-NIR spectra of a fully cured specimen (828-2-1-FC). It shows distinct peaks corresponding to the overtone bands of N-H, C-H, and O-H vibrations. The multiple overlapped spectra shown in the figure are taken from 10 different spots from a specimen. This perfect overlap of each peak in the spectra confirms the chemical uniformity (bulk scale) in the samples.

Though homogeneity is seen in the bulk, a small defect in a sample, usually created either by physical damage or heterogeneity due to the variation in chemical network structure, could lead to major differences in load bearing capabilities, potentially triggering crack initiation and finally failure. AFM-IR was used to understand the chemical network structure, especially closer to the interphase region. AFM-IR is a probe-based measurement tool that reveals the chemical composition of samples at the nanoscale. This instrument combines key elements of both nanoscale IR spectroscopy and AFM to enable the acquisition of IR spectra at spatial resolutions well beyond the optical diffraction limit. It is based on the rapid thermal expansion of materials that occurs upon absorbing IR radiation of a particular wavelength.[22], [23] The resulting AFM-IR spectra look more like absorbance spectra derived from transmission measurement FT-IR spectra. Figure 3 shows the comparison of mid-IR results obtained from traditional FT-IR and AFM-IR instrument. Though the spot size ($> 5\text{mm}$ in FTIR and $< 100\text{ nm}$ in AFM-IR) and techniques used in each of these analyses are different, the peak positions and the shapes are almost identical, which confirms the accuracy of IR results from the AFM-IR.

Figure 4 shows the topographic image and its corresponding chemical mapping of the PMC using AFM-IR. The round features in the image (Fig. 4a) are carbon fibers, and the rest is the matrix. The numbers correspond to the spots where chemical analysis is performed using the IR probe. The spots are chosen at least ~ 1 micron apart to avoid any thermal artifacts. Figure 4b shows typical IR scans (overlay), which are collected from the seven spots (Fig. 4a) covering the region from the bulk up to the interphase region. The overlay spectrum shows variation in the peak intensities, which confirms the difference in concentration of the chemical functionalities in the region. Two representative bulk spots, spot 1 and spot 2, were compared (Fig. 4c) to see if there was any variation in the spectra. Though most of the peaks are identical, there are some differences in peak intensity and relative ratio. For example, though peak intensity at 1250 cm^{-1} (epoxy) is the same, the relative ratios at 1600 cm^{-1} and 1500 cm^{-1} are different. The latter peaks are due to aromatic C-H bending peaks. That corresponds to the heterogeneity in the ratio of aromatic and epoxy peaks, which is only possible due to differences in cross-linker density in the system. Similarly, the relative peak ratios of 1383 cm^{-1} and 1361 cm^{-1} are different in those spectra. The peak close to 1383 cm^{-1} is influenced by the SO_2 peak from the hardener and the peak at 1361 cm^{-1} is due to aliphatic C-H bending. Those relative differences in the intensity further support the heterogeneity in cross-linker density. Figure 4d shows the comparison of spot 1 (bulk region) and spot 7 (interphase region). Compared to earlier results, we can see the distinct difference in intensity of the peaks as well as some shifts in the peak positions. It indicates difference in the degree of cure as well as the variation in cross-linker density. At the interphase region, the difference in reactivity due to sizing compared to the bulk system and the difficulties for prepolymers and cross-linkers to homogeneously distribute around the region lead to the differences in the network structure.

Variability seen in the chemical network structure in the interphase region also influences the properties. Thermal AFM can be used to characterize local softening processes in the polymers, made possible by the development of a new generation of heatable cantilever probes (applied voltage), which enables the detection of thermal transitions and the associated temperatures within the materials.[24] By heating a small local area rapidly (typical rates of $10^\circ\text{C}/\text{s}$), the material expands and softens to the point where the probe can penetrate the sample, which is detected as a change in the

deflection of the cantilever. With appropriate temperature calibration, using known polymers, one can create a reliable correlation between the applied voltage heating the tip and the actual temperature at the tip-sample interface. Figure 5a shows the topography image of a carbon fiber surrounded by epoxy. The numbers correspond to the spots where the thermal probe was used for the analysis. Figure 5b shows the comparison of the thermal deflection of two interphase regions, spots 6 and 7. The curves are almost identical, where a transition is seen around 150 °C. As expected, this transition temperature matches with the glass transition temperature of the epoxy found from bulk measurement by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) (Fig. 5d). Comparing the plot of the bulk (spot 1) and the interphase region (spot 6) (Fig. 5c), the slight difference in slopes supports the variation in the transition temperature. The variation in those spots is expected based on the difference seen in the chemical network structure around those regions. Similarly, peak force microscopy was used to analyze the modulus of the bulk and the interphase. The results show the clearly high modulus of the fiber and very low modulus of the bulk. Line-scan was used between the fiber and the bulk matrix to evaluate the interphase region. The results support the gradient zone where the modulus decreases going further from the fiber into the bulk.

Figure 1. a) Schematics showing interphase region of PMC, which lies between the fiber and the bulk matrix; schematics of b) epoxy (DGEBA), c) a crosslinker (3,3 DDS) and d) a cross-linked epoxy chain after reaction; e) Stress-strain curve calculated by an integrated quantum-mechanics / molecular-mechanics (QM/MM) approach of DGEBA with MDA as the crosslinking agent. Bonds begin breaking at a strain of 0.9 and are primarily between the benzylic carbon and the benzene ring and between the oxygen and the CH₂ group.

Figure 2. FT-IR spectra: a) Mid-IR region showing differences in the spectra of the reactants DGEBA and 3,3 DDS and the cured DGEBA; and b) NIR spectra of the cured product with appropriate assignment of each peak. The spectra are taken from 10 different spots from a specimen (828-2-1-FC) showing overlap of all the peaks confirming chemical uniformity in bulk.

Figure 3. Comparison of mid-IR results obtained from: a) FT-IR instrument, spot size ~ 1cm; and b) AFM-IR instrument, spot size < 100 nm.

Figure 4. Chemical mapping of the PMC using AFM-IR: a) AFM topographic image of carbon fiber epoxy composite, where the round features are carbon fibers and the rest is the matrix (with numbers corresponding to the spots where chemical analyses were performed); b) IR spectra collected from the 7 spots shown in a) covering the region from the bulk up to the interphase; c) comparison of the spectra from two bulk regions, spot 1 and spot 2, which shows some chemical variation; and d) comparison of the spectra from two regions, bulk spot 1 and interphase spot 7, which shows more chemical variation than c).

Figure 5. Thermal mapping of the PMC using AFM-TA. a) AFM topographic image of carbon fiber epoxy composite, where the round features are carbon fibers and the rest is the matrix (with numbers corresponding to the spots where the thermal analyses were performed); b) and c) are the thermal mapping plots showing probe cantilever deflection (in contact with the sample surface) vs probe tip temperature, the change in slopes caused by thermal transitions within the material. b) Comparison of two interphase regions (spots 6 and 7), where the plots are almost identical, confirming similar thermal transitions. c) Comparison of interphase (spot 6) and bulk (spot 1) where the plots have different slopes, confirming distinct thermal transitions. d) Typical differential scanning calorimetry plot (heat flux versus temperature) showing a transition region indicating the bulk-average glass transition temperature (T_g) of the polymer matrix.

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5 CONCLUSIONS

In summary, PMC samples were processed in-house with known chemical compositions to understand the chemical network structure and its influence on mechanical properties. Multiple characterization techniques combining spectroscopy, microscopy and mechanical testing were utilized to gain deeper understanding of the interphase. The key focus includes evaluating the chemical network structure a) influence of processing conditions, which include curing conditions and stoichiometric ratios, b) property between the bulk matrix and the interphase. The results confirmed that though chemical homogeneity is seen in bulk (mm scale) using spectroscopy such as FT-IR and XPS, local variations in the chemical network structure are seen at the nanoscale while analyzing via AFM-IR. Those variations are seen both in the bulk network matrix as well as at the interphase region. These variations also led to differences in thermal as well as mechanical properties. Detailed understanding of these structures and the associated properties is and will continue to be extremely valuable, enabling the validation of the current simulation effort and improving the accuracy of simulation tools as well as providing a path for virtual materials designs.

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